

Anexa 4. Analiza activităților științifice, profesionale și tehnice

Anexa 5. Previziunea activităților științifice, profesionale și tehnice

Predicted value from I1.2021-Model_1

Predicted value from I1.2022-Model_2

Predicted value from I2.2021-Model_3

Predicted value from I2.2022-Model_4

Predicted value from I3.2021-Model_5

Predicted value from I3.2022-Model_6

Predicted value from I4.2021-Model_7

Predicted value from I4.2022-Model_8

Predicted value from I5.2021-Model_9

Predicted value from I5.2022-Model_10

Predicted value from I6.2021-Model_11

Predicted value from I6.2022-Model_12

Predicted value from I7.2021-Model_13

Predicted value from I7.2022-Model_14

Predicted value from I8.2021-Model_15

Predicted value from I8.2022-Model_16

Predicted value from I10.2021-Model_17

Predicted value from I10.2022-Model_18

Predicted value from I12.2021-Model_19

Predicted value from I12.2022-Model_20

Predicted value from I13.2021-Model_21

Predicted value from I13.2022-Model_22

Predicted value from I14.2021-Model_23

Predicted value from I14.2022-Model_24

Predicted value from I15.2022-Model_26

Predicted value from I16.2021-Model_27

Predicted value from I16.2022-Model_28

Predicted value from I17.2021-Model_29

Predicted value from I17.2022-Model_30

Predicted value from I18.2021-Model_31

Predicted value from I18.2022-Model_32

Predicted value from I19.2021-Model_33

Predicted value from I19.2022-Model_34

Predicted value from I20.2021-Model_35

Predicted value from I20.2022-Model_36

Predicted value from I21.2021-Model_37

Predicted value from I21.2022-Model_38

Predicted value from I22.2021-Model_39

Predicted value from I22.2022-Model_40

Predicted value from I23.2021-Model_41

Predicted value from I23.2022-Model_42

Predicted value from I24.2022-Model_44

Predicted value from I25.2021-Model_45

Predicted value from I25.2022-Model_46

Predicted value from I26.2022-Model_48

Predicted value from I27.2021-Model_49

Predicted value from I27.2022-Model_50

Predicted value from I28.2022-Model_52

